

GC-MS analysis, antimicrobial and insecticidal activity of the leaves of *Ipomoea eriocarpa*

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Abstract : *Ipomoea eriocarpa* commonly called “sanding sulo and annual morningglories” belongs to the Convolvulaceae family. The present study deals with the GC-MS analysis, antimicrobial and insecticidal activity of the ethyl acetate (IEE) and chloroform (IEC) extracts of the leaves of the *Ipomoea eriocarpa* plant. In GC-MS analysis, three compounds were identified from the ethyl acetate extract. Chloroform extract showed antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Aspergillus niger*, however, both the extracts possess considerable insecticidal activity.

Keywords : *Ipomoea eriocarpa*, Convolvulaceae, GC-MS analysis, antimicrobial, insecticidal activity.

Introduction

Ipomoea eriocarpa (Family : Convolvulaceae) often called annual morningglories and sanding sulo, are summer annual or perennial broadleaf plants. *Ipomoea eriocarpa* R. Br. are often cultivated as ornamentals, however, they can become troublesome weeds under favorable conditions. They occur throughout the Old World tropics, tropical Asia and North Australia. The plant is occasionally consumed as an edible leafy vegetable or mixed with other food in Assam and is commonly known as “Kolmow” by them. This plant is cultivated as an arable crop in India to provide green fodder for cattle. The plant has unspecified medicinal use in India. The oil extract of the plant is used for various external applications in India such as headache, epilepsy, ulcers leprosy, rheumatism and fevers¹. An extensive literature survey revealed that the plant extract of *Ipomoea eriocarpa* was screened for its antioxidant², cerebroprotective³, antisecretory⁴, antipyretic⁵, antinociceptive⁶ and toxicity studies⁷. However, there are no reports on antimicrobial and insecticidal activity of the plant extracts. Hence, the present study is to verify the claims of the native practitioners.

Results and discussion

Preliminary phytochemical screening :

The two residues obtained were tested for various

compounds and the results obtained are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of various phytochemical screening of different extraction

Chemical constituents	IEE	IEC
Alkaloids	+	+
Carbohydrates	-	-
Glycosides	-	-
Saponins	-	+
Phytosterols	+	+
Flavonoids	-	-
Phenols	+	+
Proteins	-	-
Terpenoids	+	+

+ = Present, - = Absent.

GC-MS analysis :

The GC-MS analysis of phytocomponents in the leaves of *Ipomoea eriocarpa* revealed the presence of three phytocomponents in IEE. The phytocomponents were identified based on the peak area, retention time and molecular formula. The major phytocomponents found in IEE were shown in Table 2 as Z,Z-6,28-heptatriactontadien-2-one, 3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol (phytol) and methyl 3-bromo-1-adamantaneacetate.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the three extracts were tested for antimicrobial

Table 2. Phytocomponents identified in IEE

Sl. no.	Compounds	RT	Mol. formula	MW	Peak area (%)
1.	Z,Z-6,28-Heptatriactontadien-2-one	16.87	C ₃₇ H ₇₀ O	530	14.36
2.	3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol	17.13	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296	2.58
3.	Methyl 3-bromo-1-adamantaneacetate	29.46	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ Br	286	12.49

activity by taking different concentrations ranging from 250 to 1000 µg/ml and the results obtained are given in Table 3. IEE only showed antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* at all the concentration and *A. niger* from the concentration of 500 µg/ml and above.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of the extracts

Microorganisms	Conc. (µg/ml)	IEE	IEC	PC (10 µg/ml)	NC
<i>S. aureus</i>	250	NA	NA	10.66±0.57	-
	500	NA	NA		
	750	NA	NA		
	1000	NA	NA		
<i>E. coli</i>	250	NA	2.33±0.57	13.0±1.0	-
	500	NA	3.33±0.57		
	750	NA	5.0±1.0		
	1000	NA	6.33±1.52		
<i>A. niger</i>	250	NA	NA	10.0±1.0	-
	500	NA	1.66±0.57		
	750	NA	3.0±1.0		
	1000	1.33±0.57	4.33±1.15		

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation of the three replicates, zone of inhibition not include the diameter of the well (7 mm). PC – Positive Control, NC – Negative Control, NA – No Activity.

Insecticidal activity :

The results of the extracts were compared with the standard (chlorpyrifos). Both the extracts showed considerable insecticidal activity in comparison to the standard drug. Table 4 illustrates a significant insecticidal activity of the samples and the standard.

Table 4. Insecticidal activity of the extracts

Sl. no.	Compounds	Concentration (100 mg/2 ml)	Death time (min)
1.	IEE	100	31
2.	IEC	100	26
3.	Chlorpyrifos	100	23
4.	Control	-	-

Materials and methods :

Plant collection :

The leaves of *Ipomoea eriocarpa* have been collected from Kamrup and Udalguri district of Assam, during the month of June, 2013 and shade dried. The plant was identified as *Ipomoea eriocarpa* at the Botany Department, Gauhati University, Assam consulting the available literature and herbarium study. The voucher specimen of the plant was deposited at the college for further reference.

Preparation of extracts :

Leaves of *Ipomoea eriocarpa* were shade dried and powdered to get coarse granules. The coarse powder was subjected to continuous hot extraction in Soxhlet apparatus using two solvents namely ethyl acetate (IEE) and chloroform (IEC). The solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure, giving a greenish sticky residue (9–14% w/w). The crude extracts were stored and used for the further studies.

Preliminary phytochemical screening :

The leaves of *Ipomoea eriocarpa* was powdered and subjected to systematic phytochemical screening by successively extracting them in different solvents and testing for the presence of various phytocomponents.

GC-MS analysis :

The GC-MS analysis of IEE was performed using a Perkin-Elmer GC-MS (Perkin-Elmer Clarus 600) equipped with an Elite-5 MS silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID, 250 µm df). The oven temperature was programmed at 60 °C for 2 min then increased to 300 °C for 6 min at the rate of 10 °C/min. Helium was used as a carrier gas at the flow rate of 1 ml/min. The injector temperature was 250 °C, injection size 1 µL neat, with split ratio 10 : 1. Mass detector turbo mass gold-Perkin-Elmer was used as detector. The phytocomponents were identified after comparison with those available in the

computer library (NIST) attached to the instrument and were reported.

Antimicrobial activity :

For antimicrobial activity study two strains of bacteria and one strain of fungus was used. The bacterial isolates included a Gram-negative bacterium (*Escherichia coli*) and a Gram-positive bacterium (*Staphylococcus aureus*). The fungal isolate was *Aspergillus niger*.

The antimicrobial activity of the two extracts was tested by taking different concentrations of 250–1000 µg/ml, using agar well diffusion assay method⁸. The bacterial test organisms (*S. aureus* and *E. coli*) were grown in nutrient broth for and then spread on Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates. For *A. niger*, spore suspensions was grown in Sabor Dextrose Broth (SDB) and then spread on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates. Dimethyl formamide was used as negative control and erythromycin (10 µg) as positive control. All the tests were performed in triplicates. The antimicrobial activity was evaluated based on the diameter of zone of inhibition.

Insecticidal activity :

Insecticidal activity was carried out on termites (*Coptotermes formosanus*)^{9,10}. The test was performed using 100 mg of each of the extracts and the standard drug, chlorpyrifos. The death time of the insects was observed and reported.

Conclusion

The leaf extracts obtained gave good yield ranging from 9% to 14% w/w. The two extracts were tested for preliminary phytochemical constituents and the result obtained showed that they contain mostly alkaloids, phenols, saponins, phytosterols and terpenoids. The GC-MS analysis of IEE revealed the presence of three phytochemicals i.e. Z,Z-6,28-heptatriactontadien-2-one, 3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol and methyl 3-bromo-1-adamantaneacetate. Z,Z-6,28-Heptatriactontadien-2-one acts as vasodilator¹¹ and 3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-

hexadecen-1-ol is cancer-preventive and a constituent of chlorophyll and can be used as a precursor for the manufacture of synthetic forms of vitamin E¹² and vitamin K¹³. Antimicrobial screening of the two extracts showed that only IEC was having antimicrobial property on *E. coli* and *A. niger*, however, both the extracts showed considerable insecticidal activity in comparison to the standard drug, chloropyrifos.

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